

Supplementary Table. Source of compounds.		
ZINC ID	manufacturer	Supplier code
ZINC08275376	Enamine	T6279421
ZINC12561276	Enamine	T5944664
ZINC32561768	ChemBridge	57193933
ZINC09264647	ChemBridge	9131223
ZINC23380475	ChemBridge	54727150
ZINC19337867	ChemBridge	52123667
ZINC25562121	Enamine	T5809190
ZINC29752537	Enamine	T6206758
ZINC29036339	Enamine	T6497726
ZINC12792251	Enamine	T5999444
ZINC12903140	Enamine	T5953901
ZINC08048411	ChemBridge	9041543
ZINC19731956	Enamine	T6730351
ZINC19222149	ChemBridge	46963950
ZINC18240389	ChemBridge	5910078
ZINC09117564	Enamine	T5748403
ZINC23142787	Enamine	T6334948
ZINC23140934	Enamine	T6365385
ZINC12545208	Enamine	T6162524
ZINC22988228	Enamine	T6354799
ZINC13247129	Enamine	T6657138
ZINC31785599	Enamine	T6596653
ZINC10973809	Enamine	T6029204
ZINC20255965	ChemBridge	75179884
ZINC16667540	ChemBridge	5532994
ZINC19811667	ChemBridge	64400086
ZINC12508018	Enamine	T5250237
ZINC20745937	ChemBridge	9195953
ZINC23231889	ChemBridge	30678022
ZINC17027812	ChemBridge	7929726
ZINC32997889	Enamine	T6232937
ZINC25764343	Enamine	T5592228
ZINC10109357	Enamine	T5675064
ZINC14240853	Enamine	T5879322
ZINC30793724	Enamine	T6499332
ZINC12902053	Enamine	T6105504
ZINC24792966	Enamine	T6660640
ZINC08747729	Enamine	T5798238

Figure S1. Source of compounds.

Supplementary Table. List of protein crystal structures examined				
order	protein database ID	CSGID	resolution	Title*
1	PDB 3E4F (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00044	Resolution: 2.8Å	Title: Crystal structure of BA2930 - a putative aminoglycoside N3-acetyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
2	PDB 3O2C (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00052	Resolution: 2.35Å	Title: 2.35 Angstrom resolution structure of WeeB (VC0917), a UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2-epimerase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i>
3	PDB 3D06 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00086	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: Structure of YncA, a putative acetyltransferase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
4	PDB 3D08 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00086	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: Structure of YncA, a putative acetyltransferase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> with its cofactor acetyl-CoA
5	PDB 3D03 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00107	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Structure of IDP00107, a potential N-acetyl-gamma-glutamylphosphate reductase from <i>Shigella flexneri</i>
6	PDB 3D0Q (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00121	Resolution: 2.7Å	Title: The crystal structure of the putative tRNA synthase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2
7	PDB 3CWC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00122	Resolution: 2.23Å	Title: Crystal structure of putative glycerate kinase 2 from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2
8	PDB 3FPI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00520	Resolution: 2.8Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF 2-C-METHYL-D-ERYTHRITOL 2,4-CYCLODIPHOSPHATE SYNTHASE ISPF COMPLEXED WITH CYTIDINE TRIPHOSPHATE
9	PDB 3FPK (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01074	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF FERREDOXIN-NADP REDUCTASE FROM <i>SALMONELLA TYPHIMURIUM</i>
10	PDB 3F0B (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00046	Resolution: 1.74Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Bromoperoxidase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
11	PDB 3FF1 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00736	Resolution: 1.65Å	Title: Structure of Glucose 6-phosphate Isomerase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
12	PDB 3F6M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00520	Resolution: 2.96Å	Title: Crystal structure of 2-C-methyl-D-erythritol 2,4-cyclodiphosphate synthase IspF from <i>Yersinia pestis</i>
13	PDB 3F4N (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00439	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Pyridoxal Phosphate Biosynthetic Protein PdxJ from <i>Yersinia pestis</i>
14	PDB 3F0I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01300	Resolution: 1.88Å	Title: Arsenate reductase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i>
15	PDB 3E1F (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01530	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative succinate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2
16	PDB 3E3P (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01002	Resolution: 1.55Å	Title: Structure of IDP01002, a putative oxidoreductase from and essential gene of <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
17	PDB 3E6I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01334	Resolution: 2.9Å	Title: N-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate deacetylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i>
18	PDB 3EFV (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01530	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative succinate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2 with bound NAD
19	PDB 3EFE (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01712	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: The crystal structure of the <i>thiJ</i> /pfp family protein from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
20	PDB 3EFB (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01531	Resolution: 2.001Å	Title: Crystal structure of probable sor operon regulator from <i>Shigella flexneri</i>
21	PDB 3EER (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01325	Resolution: 1.45Å	Title: High resolution structure of a putative organic hydroperoxide resistance protein from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar eltor str. N16961
22	PDB 3EEV (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01350	Resolution: 2.61Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Chloramphenicol Acetyltransferase VCA0300 from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar eltor
23	PDB 3E3N (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00051	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: Crystal structure of the <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> phenazine biosynthesis protein, PhzF family
24	PDB 3ECT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01515	Resolution: 2.51Å	Title: Crystal Structure of the Hexapeptide-Repeat Containing-Acetyltransferase VCA0836 from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i>
25	PDB 3EC6 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01540	Resolution: 1.6Å	Title: Crystal structure of the General Stress Protein 26 from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. Sterne
26	PDB 3E9A (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01337	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Crystal structure of 2-dehydro-3-deoxyphosphoconate aldolase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar eltor str. N16961
27	PDB 3E7N (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00079	Resolution: 2.45Å	Title: Crystal structure of D-ribose high-affinity transport system from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2
28	PDB 3GRI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00795	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: The Crystal Structure of a Dihydroorotase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
29	PDB 3G0S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00571	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: The crystal structure of 2,3,4,5-tetrahydropyridine-2-carboxylate N-succinyltransferase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
30	PDB 3G0A (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01071	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: Crystal structure of the <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> FadA 3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase
31	PDB 3G09 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00573	Resolution: 1.62Å	Title: Predicted insulinase family protease from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> .
32	PDB 3G3I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00038	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF MICROCIN IMMUNITY PROTEIN MCCF FROM <i>BACILLUS ANTHRACIS</i> STR. AMES
33	PDB 3G1U (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00836	Resolution: 1.25Å	Title: 1.25 ANGSTROM CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF PYRROLIDONE-CARBOXYLATE PEPTIDASE (PCP) FROM <i>STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS</i>
34	PDB 3G2H (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01038	Resolution: 2.03Å	Title: 2-C-methyl-D-erythritol 2,4-cyclodiphosphate synthase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> .
35	PDB 3GEU (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00851	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of IcaR from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , a member of the tetracycline repressor protein family
36	PDB 3GE1 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00743	Resolution: 2.7Å	Title: 2.7 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Glycerol Kinase (glpK) from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in Complex with ADP and Glycerol
37	PDB 3G2C (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00994	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: 1.85 Angstrom Crystal Structure of O-succinylbenzoate Synthase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> in Complex with Succinic Acid
38	PDB 3GBX (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01011	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Serine hydroxymethyltransferase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
39	PDB 3GA7 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00896	Resolution: 1.55Å	Title: 1.55 Angstrom Crystal Structure of an Acetyl Esterase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
40	PDB 3G48 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01112	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: Crystal structure of chaperone CsaA from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. Ames
41	PDB 3G1Z (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01693	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: STRUCTURE OF IDP01693/YIEA, POTENTIAL T-RNA SYNTHETASE FROM <i>SALMONELLA TYPHIMURIUM</i>
42	PDB 3G2S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00743	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: 1.9 ANGSTROM CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF GLYCEROL KINASE (GLPK) FROM <i>STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS</i> IN COMPLEX WITH GLYCEROL
43	PDB 3G0M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00875	Resolution: 1.76Å	Title: Crystal structure of cysteine desulfuration protein SufE from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2
44	PDB 3G0S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01004	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: Dihydrodipicolinate synthase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2.
45	PDB 3FVW (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00427	Resolution: 2.5Å	Title: The crystal structure of the bifunctional N-acetylglucosamine-1-phosphate Uridyltransferase/Glucosamine-1-Phosphate acetyltransferase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
46	PDB 3FVX (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01357	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: The crystal structure of the peptide deformylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar El Tor str. N16961
47	PDB 3FTT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00698	Resolution: 1.6Å	Title: Crystal structure of the galactoside O-acetyltransferase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
48	PDB 3HYL (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02454	Resolution: 2.16Å	Title: Crystal structure of Transketolase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
49	PDB 3HYK (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01182	Resolution: 2.31Å	Title: 2.31 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a holo-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. Ames in complex with CoA (3',5'-ADP)
50	PDB 3HVU (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01892	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: 1.95 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Complex of Hypoxanthine-Guanine Phosphoribosyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> with 2-[N-morpholino]ethanesulfonic acid (MES)
51	PDB 3HMQ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00960	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: 1.9 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a NAD synthetase (nadE) from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> LT2 in complex with NAD(+)
52	PDB 3HL3 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01254	Resolution: 2.76Å	Title: 2.76 Angstrom Crystal Structure of a Putative Glucose-1-Phosphate Thymidyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> in Complex with a Sucrose.
53	PDB 3HIV (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01440	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: 1.7 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of an acyl carrier protein5-malonyltransferase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar eltor str. N16961
54	PDB 3HJJ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02453	Resolution: 2.15Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Maltose O-acetyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
55	PDB 3HJB (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01329	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: 1.5 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Glucose-6-phosphate Isomerase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> .
56	PDB 3HID (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00422	Resolution: 1.6Å	Title: Crystal structure of the adenylosuccinate synthetase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
57	PDB 3HFR (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00347	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: Crystal structure of glutamate racemase from <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>
58	PDB 3H83 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01892	Resolution: 2.06Å	Title: 2.06 Angstrom resolution structure of a hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase [hpt-1] from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. 'Ames Ancestor'
59	PDB 3H5O (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00692	Resolution: 1.94Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative pyrimidine-nucleoside phosphorylase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
60	PDB 3H2Y (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP90222	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Yqeh GTPase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> with dGDP Bound
61	PDB 3H1S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01808	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of superoxide dismutase from <i>Francisella tularensis</i> subsp. tularensis SCHU S4
62	PDB 3H0P (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00956	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: 2.2 Angstrom Crystal Structure of an Acyl Carrier Protein 5-malonyltransferase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> .
63	PDB 3H0Z (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00995	Resolution: 2.15Å	Title: 2.15 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Naphthoate Synthase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> .
64	PDB 3H07 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00479	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: Crystal structure of 3,4-dihydroxy-2-butanone 4-phosphate synthase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
65	PDB 3GVD (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00538	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Serine Acetyltransferase CysT from <i>Yersinia pestis</i>
66	PDB 3GSD (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00456	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: 2.05 Angstrom structure of a divalent-cation tolerance protein (CutA) from <i>Yersinia pestis</i>
67	PDB 3GSE (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00582	Resolution: 2.28Å	Title: Crystal structure of menaquinone-specific isochorismate synthase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
68	PDB 3HHS (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01131	Resolution: 1.15Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF A PHOSPHOCARRIER PROTEIN HPR FROM <i>BACILLUS ANTHRACIS</i> STR. AMES
69	PDB 3IGX (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02095	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: 1.85 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Transaldolase B (talA) from <i>Francisella tularensis</i> .
70	PDB 3IGS (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01861	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: Structure of the <i>Salmonella enterica</i> N-acetylmannosamine-6-phosphate 2-epimerase
71	PDB 3IG4 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01115	Resolution: 2.9Å	Title: Structure of a putative aminopeptidase P from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
72	PDB 3IGI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02453	Resolution: 2.6Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Maltose O-Acetyltransferase Complexed with Acetyl Coenzyme A from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
73	PDB 3IF5 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01650	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: 2.2 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Glucose-6-phosphate Isomerase (pgi) from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> .
74	PDB 3IFE (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02712	Resolution: 1.55Å	Title: 1.55 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Peptidase T (pepT-1) from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. 'Ames Ancestor'.
75	PDB 3IEB (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01486	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: Crystal structure of 3-keto-L-gulonate-6-phosphate decarboxylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar El Tor str. N16961
76	PDB 3ICC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02573	Resolution: 1.87Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative 3-oxoacyl-(acyl carrier protein) reductase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> at 1.87 Å resolution
77	PDB 3IB3 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00832	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: Crystal Structure of SACOL2612 - Coe/NonD family hydrolase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
78	PDB 3IAH (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00971	Resolution: 1.83Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Short Chain Dehydrogenase (YIC1) from <i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> serovar <i>Typhimurium</i> str. LT2 in Complex with NADP and Acetate.
79	PDB 3IAC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02065	Resolution: 2.22Å	Title: 2.2 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Glucuronate Isomerase from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> .
80	PDB 3I99 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01372	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: The crystal structure of the UDP-N-acetylenolpyruvylglucosamine reductase from the <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar E1 Tor
81	PDB 3I3W (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02164	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: STRUCTURE OF A PHOSPHOGLUCOSAMINE MUTASE FROM <i>FRANCISELLA TULARENSIS</i>
82	PDB 3I3O (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02499	Resolution: 2.06Å	Title: 2.06 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a short chain dehydrogenase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. 'Ames Ancestor' in complex with NAD-acetone
83	PDB 3I1I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01610	Resolution: 2.44Å	Title: X-ray crystal structure of homoserine O-acetyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> .
84	PDB 3I12 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00919	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: The crystal structure of the D-alanyl-alanine synthetase A from <i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> serovar <i>Typhimurium</i> str. LT2
85	PDB 3I07 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01325	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF A PUTATIVE ORGANIC HYDROPEROXIDE RESISTANCE PROTEIN FROM <i>VIBRIO CHOLERAE</i> O1BIOVAR ELTOR STR. N16961
86	PDB 3H2N (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00923	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: Structure of the <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> nfnB dihydropteridine reductase
87	PDB 3H2Q (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01970	Resolution: 1.53Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Isopenentyl-Diphosphate delta-Isomerase from <i>Salmonella enterica</i>
88	PDB 3K1S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01100	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: Crystal Structure of the PTS Cellobiose Specific Enzyme IIA from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>
89	PDB 3I2E (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00873	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: 1.8 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Dihydroorotase (pyrC) from <i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> serovar <i>Typhimurium</i> str. LT2.
90	PDB 3I7I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02355	Resolution: 2.18Å	Title: 3-deoxy-manno-oculosonate cytidyltransferase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> .
91	PDB 3IR2 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01486	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: X-ray crystal structure of the Mg-bound 3-keto-L-gulonate-6-phosphatedecarboxylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar El Tor str. N16961
92	PDB 3IWH (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00640	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Crystal structure of Rhodanese-like Domain Protein from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
93	PDB 3IY8 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01334	Resolution: 2.53Å	Title: N-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate deacetylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> complexed with fructose 6-phosphate.
94	PDB 3I5T (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00347	Resolution: 1.65Å	Title: Crystal structure of glutamate racemase from <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in complex with succinic acid
95	PDB 3I5V (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Released: 2009-09-22	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: Crystal structure of glutamate racemase from <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in complex with acetate ion
96	PDB 3IR4 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00895	Resolution: 1.2Å	Title: 1.2 Angstrom Crystal Structure of the Glutaredoxin 2 (grx8) from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> in complex with Glutathione.
97	PDB 3IRC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00272	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Crystal structure analysis of dengue-1 envelope protein domain III
98	PDB 3IQ1 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01318	Resolution: 1.67Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF DPS PROTEIN FROM <i>VIBRIO CHOLERAE</i> O1, A MEMBER OF A BROAD SUPERFAMILY OF FERRITIN-LIKE DIIRON-CARBOXYLATE PROTEINS
99	PDB 3INP (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02542	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: 2.05 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of D-ribulose-phosphate 3-epimerase from <i>Francisella tularensis</i> .
100	PDB 3IMF (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02325	Resolution: 1.99Å	Title: 1.99 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a short chain dehydrogenase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. 'Ames Ancestor'

101	PDB 3IM1 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02451	Resolution: 2.01Å	Title: 2.01 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a HIT family protein from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor'
102	PDB 3IUW (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00044	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of BA2930 in complex with CoA
103	PDB 3IUR (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02499	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: 2.05 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a short chain dehydrogenase from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor' in complex with NAD+
104	PDB 3IUI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01962	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: 1.8 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Cytosol Aminopeptidase from Coccidia burnetii
105	PDB 3IUS (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02274	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: 1.95 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of 3-deoxy-D-manno-oculosonate 8-phosphate Phosphatase from Yersinia pestis.
106	PDB 3II1 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00832	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: 1.95 Angstrom Crystal Structure of CofE/NonD family hydrolase (SACOL2612) from Staphylococcus aureus
107	PDB 3IIE (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00499	Resolution: 2.21Å	Title: 1-deoxy-D-xylose 5-phosphate reductoisomerase from Yersinia pestis.
108	PDB 3IG3 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02638	Resolution: 1.4Å	Title: 1.4Å CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF ISOCITRATE LYASE FROM YERSINIA PESTIS CO92
109	PDB 3IAY (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01826	Resolution: 2.7Å	Title: alpha-Helical barrel formed by the decamer of the zinc resistance-associated protein (STM4172) from Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium str. LT2
110	PDB 3IAC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02531	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Crystal structure of Bacillus anthracis pyrrolidone-carboxylate peptidase, pcp
111	PDB 3IAE (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02527	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: 1.5Å Crystal Structure of a hypothetical protein Imo0363 from Listeria monocytogenes EGD-e
112	PDB 3I44 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02280	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: Crystal structure of Bacillus anthracis HemeL-1, glutamate semialdehyde aminotransferase
113	PDB 3I07 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01849	Resolution: 1.88Å	Title: Methylene-tetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase/methylenetetrahydrofolate cyclohydrolase, putative bifunctional protein from Francisella tularensis.
114	PDB 3KZW (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00662	Resolution: 2.7Å	Title: Crystal structure of cytosol aminopeptidase from Staphylococcus aureus COL
115	PDB 3KZL (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00044	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: Crystal structure of BA2930 mutant (H183G) in complex with AcCoA
116	PDB 3KWO (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01964	Resolution: 1.99Å	Title: X-ray crystal structure of Putative Bacterioferritin from Campylobacter jejuni
117	PDB 3KWM (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02119	Resolution: 2.32Å	Title: Crystal structure of ribose-5-isomerase A
118	PDB 3KXJ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02458	Resolution: 2.75Å	Title: Structure of the YPO2259 putative oxidoreductase from Yersinia pestis
119	PDB 3KUI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02536	Resolution: 1.4Å	Title: Structure of the PurE Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole Carboxylase Catalytic Subunit from Yersinia pestis
120	PDB 3KQF (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02329	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: 1.8 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Enoyl-CoA Hydratase from Bacillus anthracis.
121	PDB 3KOM (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02310	Resolution: 1.6Å	Title: Crystal structure of apo Transketolase from Francisella tularensis
122	PDB 3KHY (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01739	Resolution: 1.98Å	Title: Crystal Structure of a Propionate Kinase from Francisella tularensis subsp. tularensis SCHU S4
123	PDB 3K03 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02448	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF A PHOSPHOSERINE PHOSPHOHYDROLASE-LIKE PROTEIN FROM FRANCISELLA TULARENSIS SUBSP. TULARENSIS SCHUS4
124	PDB 3KBO (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00051	Resolution: 2.14Å	Title: 2.14 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Putative Oxidoreductase (ycdW) from Salmonella typhimurium in Complex with NADP.
125	PDB 3K88 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01892	Resolution: 2.09Å	Title: 2.09 Angstrom resolution structure of a hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (hpt-1) from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor' in complex with GMP
126	PDB 3K96 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01976	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: 2.1 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (gpsA) from Coccidia burnetii.
127	PDB 3K28 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02781	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF A GLUTAMATE-1-SEMIALDEHYDE AMINOTRANSFERASE FROM BACILLUS ANTHRACIS WITH BOUND PYRIDOXAL 5'PHOSPHATE
128	PDB 3N0S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00044	Resolution: 2.15Å	Title: Crystal structure of BA2930 mutant (H183A) in complex with AcCoA
129	PDB 3MZZ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00640	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Rhodanese-like Domain Protein from Staphylococcus aureus
130	PDB 3MSZ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01801	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Glutaredoxin 1 from Francisella tularensis Complexed with Cacydylate
131	PDB 3MSU (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04634	Resolution: 1.84Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Citrate Synthase from Francisella tularensis
132	PDB 3MJD (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02311	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: 1.9 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Orotate Phosphoribosyltransferase (pyrE) Francisella tularensis.
133	PDB 3MIF (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04490	Resolution: 1.47Å	Title: Phosphoribosylamine-glycine ligase from Yersinia pestis.
134	PDB 3MGA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00118	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: 2.4 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Ferric Enterobactin Esterase (fes) from Salmonella typhimurium.
135	PDB 3M84 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04643	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole Synthetase from Francisella tularensis
136	PDB 3M5P (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02733	Resolution: 1.65Å	Title: Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase from Francisella tularensis complexed with fructose-6-phosphate.
137	PDB 3M49 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP03454	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Transketolase Complexed with Thiamine Diphosphate from Bacillus anthracis
138	PDB 3M3H (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04423	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: 1.75 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of an orotate phosphoribosyltransferase from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor'
139	PDB 3M07 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00968	Resolution: 1.4Å	Title: 1.4 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Putative alpha Amylase from Salmonella typhimurium.
140	PDB 3YL (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00334	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: Structure of 3-oxoacyl-acyl carrier protein reductase, FabG from Francisella tularensis
141	PDB 3LUS (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01325	Resolution: 1.96Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative organic hydroperoxide resistance protein with molecule of captopril bound in one of the active sites from Vibrio cholerae
142	PDB 3LIJ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02710	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Structure of Imo2462, a Listeria monocytogenes amidohydrolase family putative dipeptidase
143	PDB 3LQN (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02609	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Crystal Structure of CBS Domain-containing Protein of Unknown Function from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor'
144	PDB 3LNO (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02795	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Domain of Unknown Function DUF59 from Bacillus anthracis
145	PDB 3LJK (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02733	Resolution: 1.48Å	Title: Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase from Francisella tularensis.
146	PDB 3LHQ (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02616	Resolution: 1.56Å	Title: DNA-binding transcriptional repressor AcrR from Salmonella typhimurium.
147	PDB 3LGC (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01801	Resolution: 2.77Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Glutaredoxin 1 from Francisella tularensis
148	PDB 3O02 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00688	Resolution: 2.37Å	Title: 2.37 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of an alanine racemase (alr) from Staphylococcus aureus subsp. aureus COL
149	PDB 3OKF (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04176	Resolution: 2.5Å	Title: 2.5 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of 3-Dehydroquinase Synthase (aroB) from Vibrio cholerae
150	PDB 3O1C (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04122	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: Crystal structure of a putative Asp/Glu Racemase from Yersinia pestis
151	PDB 3OGA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01880	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: 1.75 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a putative NTP pyrophosphohydrolase (yfaO) from Salmonella typhimurium LT2
152	PDB 3OFS (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02289	Resolution: 1.52Å	Title: Crystal Structure of a Dethiobiotin Synthetase from Francisella tularensis subsp. tularensis SCHU S4
153	PDB 3O7M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01634	Resolution: 1.98Å	Title: 1.98 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (hpt-2) from Bacillus anthracis str. 'Ames Ancestor'
154	PDB 3O6V (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04345	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: Crystal structure of Uridine Phosphorylase from Vibrio cholerae O1 biovar El Tor
155	PDB 3O1K (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01380	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF PUTATIVE DIHYDRONEOPTERIN ALDOLASE (FOLB) FROM VIBRIO CHOLERA O1 BIOVAR EL TOR STR N16961
156	PDB 3O04 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP05301	Resolution: 1.85Å	Title: Crystal structure of the beta-keto-acyl carrier protein synthase II (Imo2201) from Listeria monocytogenes
157	PDB 3NZT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01828	Resolution: 2Å	Title: 2.0 Angstrom Crystal structure of Glutamate-Cysteine Ligase (gshA) from Francisella tularensis in Complex with AMP.
158	PDB 3NZ2 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01515	Resolution: 2.35Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Hexapeptide-Repeat Containing-Acetyltransferase, VCA0836 from Vibrio cholerae O1 biovar eltor
159	PDB 3NX4 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00076	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of the yHd oxidoreductase from Salmonella enterica in complex with NADP
160	PDB 3NVT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00348	Resolution: 1.95Å	Title: 1.95 Angstrom crystal structure of a bifunctional 2'-deoxy-7-phosphoheptulonate synthase/chorismate mutase (aroA) from Listeria monocytogenes EGD-e
161	PDB 3NUA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04560	Resolution: 1.4Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole-Succinocarboxamide Synthase from Clostridium perfringens
162	PDB 3NXT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04466	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal Structure of L-asparaginase I from Yersinia pestis
163	PDB 3NAV (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04160	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF AN ALPHA SUBUNIT OF TRYPTOPHAN SYNTHASE FROM VIBRIO CHOLERA O1 BIOVAR EL TOR STR N16961
164	PDB 3N8H (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02771	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Pantoate-beta-alanine Ligase Complexed with AMP from Francisella tularensis
165	PDB 3N77 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01880	Resolution: 1.86Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF IDP01880, PUTATIVE NTP PYROPHOSPHOHYDROLASE OF SALMONELLA TYPHIMURIUM LT2
166	PDB 3N5M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01705	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: Crystals structure of a Bacillus anthracis aminotransferase
167	PDB 3N0M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00044	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: Crystal structure of BA2930 mutant (H183G) in complex with AcCoA
168	PDB 3P7M (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02372	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Structure of putative lactate dehydrogenase from Francisella tularensis subsp. tularensis SCHU S4
169	PDB 3N2A (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP09074	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF BIFUNCTIONAL POLY(POLYGLUTAMATE SYNTHASE/DIHYDROFOLATE SYNTHASE COMPLEXED WITH ADP FROM YERSINIA PESTIS CO92
170	PDB 3P54 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00254	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: Crystal Structure of the Japanese Encephalitis Virus Envelope Protein, strain SA-14-14-2.
171	PDB 3P2L (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02821	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: Crystal Structure of ATP-dependent Clp Protease Subunit P from Francisella tularensis
172	PDB 3P2A (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04482	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Thioresoxin 2 from Yersinia pestis
173	PDB 3P0R (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04035	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Crystal structure of azoreductase from Bacillus anthracis str. Sterne
174	PDB 3P09 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02545	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Beta-Lactamase from Francisella tularensis
175	PDB 3P0B (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00523	Resolution: 1.91Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Beta-Lactamase/D-Alanine Carboxypeptidase from Yersinia pestis
176	PDB 3OYT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00577	Resolution: 1.84Å	Title: 1.84 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of 3-oxoacyl-acyl carrier protein synthase I (fabB) from Yersinia pestis CO92
177	PDB 3OXP (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04293	Resolution: 1.2Å	Title: Structure of phosphotransferase enzyme II, A component from Yersinia pestis CO92 at 1.2 Å resolution
178	PDB 3OWA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04432	Resolution: 1.97Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Acyl-CoA Dehydrogenase complexed with FAD from Bacillus anthracis
179	PDB 3OJT (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00335	Resolution: 1.65Å	Title: Crystal structure of glutamate racemase from Francisella tularensis subsp. tularensis SCHU S4 in complex with D-glutamate.
180	PDB 3OUG (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02730	Resolution: 1.55Å	Title: Crystal structure of cleaved L-aspartate-alpha-decarboxylase from Francisella tularensis
181	PDB 3O7S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01656	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: 2.2 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of putative UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2-epimerase from Listeria monocytogenes
182	PDB 3O7I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04323	Resolution: 1.16Å	Title: Crystal structure of VC2308 protein
183	PDB 3OSU (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP05774	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of the 3-oxoacyl-acyl carrier protein reductase, FabG, from Staphylococcus aureus
184	PDB 3OS6 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01205	Resolution: 2.4Å	Title: Crystal structure of putative 2,3-dihydroxybenzoate-specific isochorismate synthase, Dhbc from Bacillus anthracis.
185	PDB 3OQ3 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP05773	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: Structural Basis of Type-I Interferon Sequestration by a Poxvirus Decoy Receptor
186	PDB 3O9K (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01083	Resolution: 1.9Å	Title: Crystal structure of divalent-cation tolerance protein CutA from Salmonella enterica
187	PDB 3O9Q (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04072	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Phosphoribosylaminoimidazole carboxylase with fructose-6-phosphate bound to the central channel of the octameric protein structure.
188	PDB 3OOW (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Released: 2010-11-17	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: Octameric structure of the phosphoribosylaminoimidazole carboxylase catalytic subunit from Francisella tularensis subsp. tularensis SCHU S4.
189	PDB 3QM2 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00945	Resolution: 2.25Å	Title: 2.25 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Phosphoserine Aminotransferase (SerC) from Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium
190	PDB 3QUG (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00629	Resolution: 2.04Å	Title: Epidermin biosynthesis protein Epid from Staphylococcus aureus.
191	PDB 3QFH (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00624	Resolution: 2.05Å	Title: 2.05 Angstrom Resolution Crystal Structure of Epidermin Leader Peptide Processing Serine Protease (EpiP) from Staphylococcus aureus.
192	PDB 3QDN (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01793	Resolution: 2.09Å	Title: Putative thioresoxin protein from Salmonella typhimurium.
193	PDB 3OQA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02050	Resolution: 1.87Å	Title: THE CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF THE N-TERMINAL DOMAIN OF A MERR-LIKE TRANSCRIPTIONAL REGULATOR FROM LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES EGD-E
194	PDB 3O3Q (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01865	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: THE CRYSTAL STRUCTURE OF FRUCTOSE 1,6-BISPHOSPHATE ALDOLASE FROM BACILLUS ANTHRACIS STR. 'AMES ANCESTOR'
195	PDB 3Q88 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02733	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase from Francisella tularensis complexed with ribose 1,5-bisphosphate.
196	PDB 3Q7H (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02028	Resolution: 2.5Å	Title: Structure of the ClpP subunit of the ATP-dependent Clp Protease from Coccidia burnetii
197	PDB 3Q7I (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02733	Resolution: 1.54Å	Title: Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase from Francisella tularensis complexed with 6-phosphogluconic acid.
198	PDB 3Q6D (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01139	Resolution: 1.97Å	Title: Xaa-Pro dipeptidase from Bacillus anthracis.
199	PDB 3Q58 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04524	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Structure of N-acetylmannosamine-6-Phosphate Epimerase from Salmonella enterica
200	PDB 3Q1K (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00919	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: The Crystal Structure of the D-alanyl-alanine Synthetase A from Salmonella enterica Typhimurium Complexed with ADP

201	PDB 3P2S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04384	Resolution: 1.89Å	Title: Crystal Structure of a pyridoxamine kinase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> CO92
202	PDB 3PP8 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00951	Resolution: 2.1Å	Title: 2.1 Angstrom Crystal Structure of Putative Oxidoreductase (ycdW) from <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> .
203	PDB 3PP9 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00047	Resolution: 1.6Å	Title: 1.6 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of putative streptothricin acetyltransferase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. Ames in complex with acetyl coenzyme A
204	PDB 3PN5 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04345	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Uridine Phosphorylase from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> Complexed with Uracil
205	PDB 3PGY (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00749	Resolution: 1.92Å	Title: Serine hydroxymethyltransferase from <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , S9SP mutant.
206	PDB 3PEI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00067	Resolution: 2.69Å	Title: 2.7 Angstrom resolution crystal structure of a probable holliday junction DNA helicase (ruvB) from <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> NCTC 11168 in complex with adenosine-5'-diphosphate
207	PDB 3PEI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02398	Resolution: 2.7Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Cytosol Aminopeptidase from <i>Francisella tularensis</i>
208	PDB 3PEA (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04689	Resolution: 1.82Å	Title: Crystal structure of enoyl-CoA hydratase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> str. 'Ames Ancestor'
209	PDB 3RJ4 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01750	Resolution: 1.75Å	Title: Crystal Structure of 7-cyano-7-deazaguanine Reductase, QueF from <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> O1 biovar El Tor
210	PDB 3RJI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00523	Resolution: 1.5Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Beta-lactamase/D-alanine Carboxypeptidase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> complexed with citrate
211	PDB 3RHI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04601	Resolution: 2.48Å	Title: DNA-binding protein HU from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> .
212	PDB 3RF0 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP02550	Resolution: 1.8Å	Title: Crystal Structure of Exopolyphosphatase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i>
213	PDB 3RE3 (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00331	Resolution: 2.65Å	Title: Crystal Structure of 2-C-Methyl-D-Erythritol 2,4-Cyclodiphosphate Synthase from <i>Francisella tularensis</i>
214	PDB 3RDW (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP00581	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: Putative arsenate reductase from <i>Yersinia pestis</i> .
215	PDB 3ROI (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01842	Resolution: 2.2Å	Title: 2.20 Angstrom resolution structure of 3-phosphoshikimate 1-carboxyvinyltransferase (AroA) from <i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
216	PDB 3R8Y (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01143	Resolution: 1.7Å	Title: Structure of the <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> tetrahydropicolinate succinyltransferase
217	PDB 3RSX (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01207	Resolution: 2Å	Title: Crystal Structure of D-alanine--D-Alanine Ligase from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> complexed with ATP
218	PDB 3R3S (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01048	Resolution: 1.25Å	Title: Structure of the YghA Oxidoreductase from <i>Salmonella enterica</i>
219	PDB 3R3R (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP01056	Resolution: 1.2Å	Title: Structure of the YrdA ferrispyochelin binding protein from <i>Salmonella enterica</i>
220	PDB 3R3T (PDBSUM) (Profunc) (GPSS) (MMDB)	Target IDP04069	Resolution: 2.3Å	Title: Crystal Structure of 30S Ribosomal Protein S from <i>Bacillus anthracis</i>

*those in blue font denote structures selected for further investigation

Figure S2. List of Protein Crystal Structures Examined. The first 220 crystal structures deposited into the Protein Database (PDB) from the Center for Structural Genomics of Infectious Diseases (CSGID) are listed.

Supplementary Table. Rank order binding of compounds to protein pockets

Rank	Dxr1			Dxr2		
	ZINC ID*	Smiles**	Score	ZINC ID	Smiles	Score
1	ZINC20136854	Cc1c(c2c(n1)CN(C2)c3ccc(n3)C)4nc(4)C5CC5	-112.851	ZINC08275376	Cc1c(snn1)C(=O)OCCn2c3ccc(c3)nH)c2=O	-71.031
2	ZINC17017832	c1ccc-2c(c1)CCc3c2c3c(c3)C(=O)N(C)CC(=O)O]O-	-104.029	ZINC07126183	OC1c1ccc1C=CC2(NH+)=C(N=C3N2c4cccc4N3)N	-70.369
3	ZINC08582280	c1ccc(ccc1c1)[O-]NCC2CCNc3c(c(n3)N)O]N2	-103.413	ZINC14215480	c1ccc2c(c1)[nH]c(=O)n2C2CCO(=O)c3ccc3c	-69.707
4	ZINC12561276	c1ccc2c(c1)[nH]c3n2c(n3)SC4ccc(4)C(=O)]O-	-103.201	ZINC12508018	CCn1c2ccc(c2)n1c3c3nc(n3)N]C(=O)]O-	-69.576
5	ZINC26472880	c1ccc(c1)c2cn2[nH]n2)S3c3nc(n3)N]N	-103.117	ZINC23144933	Cc1c2ccc(ccc2on1)CN3CCCC(C3)c4cc(=O)[nH]n4	-69.299
6	ZINC19782199	c1ccc(c1)C(C)C(=O)N2CC2nnc2)c3ccc3	-102.520	ZINC20906985	c1ccc(cen1)C(=O)N2CCN(C(=O)C2)C3CCC(C3)c4c[nH]n4	-69.278
7	ZINC19224863	CC(Cn1nncn1)NC(=O)C2CCc3ccc3c2	-101.869	ZINC22012024	c1ccc(ccc1Cc2c[nH]c3c2c(=O)[nH]c3)N]C(=O)]O-	-68.767
8	ZINC20820275	Cc1cc(=O)n1)CC(=O)NCC2c2nc(c3c(n2)CCCC3)C	-101.352	ZINC31285082	Cc1c(c(=O)[nH]c1)n1)CC(=O)Nc2ccc3c(c2)[nH]c1=O]o3	-68.472
9	ZINC32540617	CC(C)1nc1c(n1)CN2c2(ncf(n2)c3ccc4ccc4o3)N	-99.204	ZINC12323067	c1ccc2(c1)c1)OC(=O)NCC3ccc3	-67.981
10	ZINC19228137	Cc1cc(nc1)CCN(C=O)Nc2[n-]nnc2)C(F)F	-99.146	ZINC12152422	CCc1c(c1)C(=O)C(=O)OCCN2c3ccc3c3)nH)c2=O	-67.955
11	ZINC05762780	c1ccc(c1)C(=O)C2[nH]n2)N2)Cn3cn3	-98.961	ZINC32511762	Cc1ccc2(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)C3nc(c3)N4CCCC(C4)C#N	-67.626
12	ZINC12146860	Cc1nccn1CCN(C=O)c2cc([nH]n2)c3ccc3	-98.932	ZINC04761086	c1c2c(c1)c1)N3CCCC3)F]n(c2)N]C(=O)N	-67.556
13	ZINC32501669	c1ccc2c(c1)[nH]c2)SCc3[nH]c3)C4ccc4	-98.894	ZINC19238547	Cc1ccsc1C(=O)N2CC(C)C2)c3c4c([nH]n3)ncn4	-67.462
14	ZINC20136854	Cc1c(c2c(n1)CN(C2)c3ccc(n3)C)4nc(4)C5CC5	-98.471	ZINC23399754	c1c2c1c(c1)O)N3CCCC(C3)c4cc(=O)[nH]c4)CCCC2	-67.367
15	ZINC23465885	c1ccc(c1)Nc2nc2c(C(=O)N)CC3c(c3)O]nH]n3	-98.090	ZINC17312810	C(CSN=Nc1[nH]c2c1)C(=O)[nH]c2)N]O	-67.306
16	ZINC20136854	Cc1c(c2c(n1)CN(C2)c3ccc(n3)C)4nc(4)C5CC5	-97.447	ZINC17312810	C(CSN=Nc1[nH]c2c1)C(=O)[nH]c2)N]O	-67.306
17	ZINC14988217	C(C(=O)O)O]Nc1c(n1)C2c2c2)CCC(=O)O]	-97.352	ZINC12792251	CCCCOC1(NH+)=C(N=C2N1c3ccc3N)N	-67.037
18	ZINC20136854	Cc1c(c2c(n1)CN(C2)c3ccc(n3)C)4nc(4)C5CC5	-97.281	ZINC16368852	CCCCOC1(NH+)=C(N=C2N1c3ccc3N)N	-66.834
19	ZINC19744740	c1ccc(c1)F)c2c3c([nH]n2)CCN(C3)c4ccc5c4en[nH]5	-97.038	ZINC16368852	CCCCOC1(NH+)=C(N=C2N1c3ccc3N)N	-66.834
20	ZINC20219867	c1ccc(c1)c2cc2)COC(=O)N2)C3ccc3n4cnc4	-96.959	ZINC17682020	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)C3c[nH]c3)N]C(=O)c4c[nH]c5c4ccc5	-66.799
21	ZINC29036339	c1ccc(c1)n2c(nnn2)NC3ccc(c3)n4cnc4	-96.844	ZINC12147225	CCC1c(nc2ccc2c2n1)C(=O)NCC3ccc([nH]n3)C4C4)CC	-66.792
22	ZINC23465967	Cc1ccc(s1)CN(C)O)N2nc2([nH]n2)C3ccc3F	-96.801	ZINC19939112	c1ccc(cc1)c2ccc2c2n3cnc4c3c(=O)[nH]c4)O]N	-66.750
23	ZINC05135171	CCC(C(=O)]O-)]n1c(=O)c2cc3c(n2cn1)cc3	-96.734	ZINC32741542	c1ccc2ccc3c2c(1)N(S3)=O)O)CC5c4n(c1)N]n4	-66.563
24	ZINC04772496	c1ccc2cc1cc1Cc3cnc4c(n3)C(=O)n4)N)OC2	-96.616	ZINC06448865	c1ccc(cc1)c2nnc(o2)SCc3c(=O)[nH]c4ccc4n3	-66.337
25	ZINC07719377	CO1ccc(cc1)C(=O)N2c2(nc2n2)N)O	-96.579	ZINC20520905	c1ccc2c(c1)C(=O)N3CCCC(C3)c4cc(=O)[nH]c4)ncs2	-66.324
26	ZINC23380475	Cc1[nH]n2c(c1)CN(C=O)c2cc([nH]n2)c3ccc3	-96.496	ZINC14268197	c1ccc(cc1)CC(=O)N2ccc3c(c2)[nH]c3)C(=O)[nH]3	-66.185
27	ZINC32547811	c1ccc(cc1)c2cc2c(C(=O)N)C(=O)]c3[nH]c3	-96.328	ZINC12945191	c1ccc2c(c1)nc(o2)COc1(C)C3CC(=O)Nc4C3ccc(c4)F	-66.024
28	ZINC12360046	c1ccc2c(c1)C(=C2)C(=O)CO]NCC(=O)O]O-	-96.267	ZINC14351330	c1ccc(cc1)n2cc(=O)N2)C3ccc4nnnn4n3	-65.909
29	ZINC23916933	c1ccc(c1)c2c3c(c1)ncn3)N4CCCC(C4)C(=O)]O]n2	-95.963	ZINC35683323	c1ccc2c(c1)C(=O)[nH]2)C(=O)O)Cn3cnc4c3ccc4	-65.829
30	ZINC19113065	Cc1nc(n1)c2ccc(nc2)c3ccc(c3)c4cnc1)4)CC=C	-95.698	ZINC19798798	c1ccc(cc1)F]C2(COC2)Cn3c4cc4c3)cn[nH]n4	-65.342
31	ZINC19782117	Cc1cc(n1)C(=O)N]C(=O)CCn2nc2n2)c3ccc3c3	-95.662	ZINC04810508	c1ccc(cc1)N(C2c2c3ccc3c3)nH)c2=O)C(=O)c4c[nH]n4	-65.152
32	ZINC16951305	c1ccc(cc1)C=C2cnc3c2)C(=O)nc3)N]O]C(=O)]O-	-95.651	ZINC26714918	c1ccc2c(c1)CN2CCCNC3ccc4nnnn4n3	-64.981
33	ZINC15783075	CC(C1nc1n1)2cnc2)N]C(=O)OC3ccc3	-95.589	ZINC05360588	COC(=O)C1ccc(O)CO(=O)c2c3ccc3c3]nH]n2	-64.972
34	ZINC18445433	c1ccc(cc1)c2cc2c(C(=O)N)C(=O)]c3[nH]n3	-95.525	ZINC20512725	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)C3c[nH]c3)N]C(=O)]n4	-64.964
35	ZINC20995358	c1ccc(cc1)N2CC(C)2)CN(C=O)c3cc(=O)[nH]c3]O-	-95.489	ZINC19771170	Cc1c1sc(n1)C(=O)N2c2ccc3c2c2)[nH]c(=O)[nH]3	-64.944
36	ZINC14163274	c1ccc(c1)n2c(c3c2)NC(=O)C(C3c4ccc4)CN	-95.410	ZINC20915477	c1ccc(c2c[nH]c2)c1)C3nc(n3)CCn4cnc4	-64.536
37	ZINC16689462	Cc1ccc2nc1n2c2)S3C(=O)NCC3CCCC3	-95.233	ZINC14123481	Cc1ccc2c1)oc2C(=O)N3CC(=O)Nc4C3ccc4	-64.503
38	ZINC22002208	c1ccc(cc1)C(=O)]O-)]NCC2n2c2c2n2)C]c3=O	-95.060	ZINC12146876	Cc1c1(c[nH]n1)C)CN(C(=O)c2c3c(nH)2)CCCC3	-64.430
39	ZINC20998451	c1ccc2c(c1)nn2C2c3nc(n3)C4ccc4	-95.044	ZINC09644478	c1ccc2c(c1)c3nc(n3)C(=O)[nH]2)Cn4cnc5C4ccc5	-64.141
40	ZINC30991478	Cn1ccsc1N=C(=O)CC(C(=O)N)2CC(=O)N3c2ccc3	-94.954	ZINC20982583	Cc1nnc2=O)cc(nc2s1)C5c3c([nH]n3)N	-64.030
41	ZINC32026329	Cc1c(c1)C(=O)CC1)OC2ccc(cc2)c3nc(n3)C(=O)N	-94.860	ZINC23580734	c1ccc(cc1)c3c([nH]n2)C3ccc(c3)c4c[nH]n4	-63.947
42	ZINC16079956	c1ccc2c(c1)nc2n2)c3ccc(c3)nc3C4ccc4)O]CN	-94.834	ZINC19719481	Cn1cc(n1)c2cnc2C3CC(=O)N(C3)c4ccc4)OC	-63.822
43	ZINC30028008	c1ccc(c1)c2c2c([nH]n2)C(=O)OC3mnn3C4CC4	-94.694	ZINC07625220	Cc1ccc(nc1)S5c2nc(n2)N]N)c3ccc3	-63.708
44	ZINC12561239	Cc1ncc2c(c2s1)Nc3ccc4nnnn4n3	-94.692	ZINC4526292	c1ccc(ccc1CCN2c2c2)C3ccc3	-63.645
45	ZINC23311107	c1ccc(cc1)c2nc2c(s2)NC(=O)Nc3c4c([nH]n3)CCC4	-94.663	ZINC23145424	CC1C2ccc(ccc2o1)C(=O)N3CC(C)C3)c4cc(=O)[nH]cn4	-63.539
46	ZINC19117121	Cc1cc(nc1)C2)CCCN(C2)C(=O)C3ccc3c3	-94.431	ZINC32741542	c1ccc2ccc3c2c(1)N(S3)=O)O)CC5c4n(c1)N]n4	-63.339
47	ZINC26421097	CC1C2ccc(cc2o1)c3cc(n3)C(=O)]O-	-94.370	ZINC22002208	c1ccc(ccc1)O-)]NCC2n2c2c2n2)C]c3=O	-63.290
48	ZINC19655561	Cc1c(c1)C(=O)N]C(=O)CC(C)C2(C)C2(C)C2	-94.327	ZINC11616082	Cc1c(cnc1)c2cc(c2)N2)S3C3cc(=O)[nH]c(=O)[nH]3)CN	-63.256
49	ZINC05957007	COC(=O)c1ccc(cc1)COC(=O)N2)CC2C(=O)]O]	-94.240	ZINC23598229	c1ccc(cc1)CN2cnc2n2)N3cn3	-63.172
50	ZINC11492191	Cc1ccc(cc1n2ccc2)C(=O)OC3c3nc(n3)N]N	-94.192	ZINC23145872	Cc1[nH]c(=O)cc1)CN(C(=O)c2cn(c3c2ccc3)C	-63.046
51	ZINC21982687	c1ccc(c1)C(=O)OC2CO(C)2(C)O]O]	-93.701	ZINC20166597	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C3ccc3C2CN(C=O)C4CCCN(C4)C(=O)N	-62.907
52	ZINC29024005	CC1nnc1)COC(=O)c2ccc(c2)c3nc(n3)C	-93.670	ZINC15256353	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C3ccc3c2c2)C3nc(n3)O)nc(n2)O	-62.690
53	ZINC14746202	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C[nH]2)c3c[nH]c3)C(=O)c4c[nH]c5c4ccc5	-93.668	ZINC08625735	CCCCOC(=O)c1ccc(=O)[nH]c2c1ccc2	-62.642
54	ZINC13312152	Cc1ccc(cc1)C1c2ccc(cc2)C(=O)]O]OC(C=O)]O-	-93.614	ZINC09264467	c1ccc(cc1)N2]nH]c(=O)cc(n2)C5c3ccc3	-62.608
55	ZINC04830524	c1ccc(cc1)N)S5C2c2c(nc2n2)N]N	-93.613	ZINC32561768	CC1c2c([nH]n1)CN(C2)C(=O)c3ccc3c3)c4ccc4)O4	-62.512
56	ZINC13693309	Cc1ccc(n1)C1c2c(n2)C(=O)]O-)]c3ccc3c3)OC	-93.567	ZINC08586194	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)[nH]2)C5c3ccc3	-62.436
57	ZINC05531203	c1cc2c3ccc4(=O)[nH]c(=O)nc4o3cc5c2c1c1)O)c5=O	-93.552	ZINC30005705	CC(c1ccc2ccc2o1)N(C)C3c3nnn3C4cccc4	-62.346
58	ZINC19124373	Cc1cc(=O)n1)2cnc2c3ccc(nc3)N4CCCC4	-93.339	ZINC11658316	Cc1nc([nH]n1)S5C(=O)c2ccc3c2)C4cccc4C3	-62.301
59	ZINC20136854	Cc1c(c2c(n1)CN(C2)c3ccc(n3)C)4nc(4)C5CC5	-93.323	ZINC19112822	Cc1c1(nH]c1)CN(C)C(=O)c2ccc(c2)c3c[nH]n3	-62.253
60	ZINC19111859	CC(C)CN1cnc2c1c(=O)nc1)C2=O)N3ccc(c3)C1	-93.297	ZINC32974152	c1ccc(ccc1)CN(C(=O)N2CC2)C3ccc3	-62.215
61	ZINC04997834	Cc1ccc(cc1)C(=O)CC(C(=O)]O-)]n2cnc2	-93.277	ZINC19744740	c1ccc(cc1)F)c2c3c([nH]n2)CCN(C3)c4ccc5c4en[nH]5	-62.197
62	ZINC14805447	c1ccc(cc1)n2nc(n2)SC3c3nc(n3)N]N	-93.168	ZINC20530255	c1ccc(cc1)c2c3ccc3c3)nH]c(=O)c2S5CO	-62.188
63	ZINC35426082	c1ccc(cc1)N2CC2c3c3c(n3)c4cnc4N	-93.156	ZINC32511762	Cc1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)C3nc(c3)N4CCCC(C4)C#N	-62.036
64	ZINC27820520	c1ccc(nnc1n2ccc2)N3CCC(C)C(=O)]O-	-93.141	ZINC11107116	c1ccc(cc1)CN2nnc2S5c3cnc(n3)N]N	-61.943
65	ZINC20779847	Cc1ccc2c1S5C(=O)N]C1(C)c2cnc2	-93.041	ZINC17024390	CC1c2c3ccc3c3)nH]c2nc1)O	-61.934
66	ZINC04963604	c1ccc(cc1)C(=O)]O-)]NCC(C(=O)Nc2c(nc2n2)N]N	-92.988	ZINC19455599	CC(C)CC1ccc1)N(C=O)c2c3c3c([nH]c2=O)CCC3	-61.891
67	ZINC32587203	c1cc2c(cc1c3ccc4c3)OCOC4)c(=O)[nH]n2	-92.904	ZINC23141629	c1ccc2c(c1)cc(o2)CC(=O)N3c1)Cn3	-61.834
68	ZINC07373202	Cc1ccc(n1)COC(=O)c2ccc3c2)NC(=O)CN3CCC4	-92.899	ZINC22009138	CNS(=O)=O)CC1ccc2c1c1)C(=O)[nH]2)S3ccc3	-61.828
69	ZINC09117564	c1ccc(cc1)n2cc2)C(=O)OC3c3nc4ccc4c3)N3	-92.875	ZINC25562121	c1ccc(cc1)c1)S5COC(=O)c2cnc2)N(C)F)F	-61.828
70	ZINC19337867	Cc1ccc(nc1)CCN(C(=O)C)N2cnc2)C	-92.837	ZINC23429798	Cc1c1c(n1)c2ccc2)C)C3ccc(n4c3)nc(n4)C(=O)]O-	-61.809
71	ZINC14119639	c1ccc(c1)Cn2cc(c2)c3ccc4c3)OCOC4)CO	-92.829	ZINC20865973	c1ccc(cc1)c2nc(s2)CN3CC4c4c[nH]4)C3	-61.806
72	ZINC19369061	c1ccc(cc1)C(=O)CN2c2(=O)cc3c2)CCCC3	-92.825	ZINC19988818	c1ccc(cc1)C2CCN(C2)C(=O)c3c[nH]c(=O)[nH]c3=O	-61.731
73	ZINC17058056	c1ccc(cc1)CCC2=N3c(nc3)OC2)N]O	-92.780	ZINC05661495	COc1ccc(c1)C(=O)c2cc([nH]c2)C(=O)NCC3ccc3	-61.701
74	ZINC06411783	COc1ccc-2cc-3n(c1c2c1=O)CCc4ccc3c5c4)OCOS	-92.762	ZINC01620723	Cn1c(nc2c1c(=O)[nH]c(=O)n2)C)C3ccc3	-61.689
75	ZINC12195325	Cc1ccc(cc1)c2nc(n2)CN(C=O)c3c(nc3)C(C)C	-92.759	ZINC23380348	Cc1ccc(cc1)n2cc(c2)c3ccc(n3)N4C4cc4)O4	-61.680
76	ZINC15729907	c1ccc2c(c1)cc([nH]2)c3nc(n3)CN4c5ccc5OCC4=O	-92.751	ZINC20534310	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)[nH]2)CC(=O)N3CC4(C)CCC4)OC3	-61.625
77	ZINC09437918	COC1ccc(cc1)OC2cc2(=O)oc3c2cc4c3)CCC4)CN	-92.742	ZINC12815164	Cc1ccc2c(c1)nc2)NC3ccc3c3)c4c4c4)N]C	-61.530
78	ZINC32587099	Cc1ncc1)CN2ccc2)N3CCCOC3	-92.742	ZINC32582029	CCc1c(nc1)C(=O)N2CC(C)C2)c3cc(=O)[nH]c3)C	-61.513
79	ZINC20233833	c1ccc(cc1)C(F)F)F)C(=O)NCCc2[n-]nnc2)Cl	-92.599	ZINC32541020	Cc1ccc2c1nnc2(=O)CCS3(nH]n3	-61.481
80	ZINC20536424	CCC(C)O)C1nnc1)N(C(=O)N)C2c2c2n2	-92.555	ZINC05090674	COC(=O)c1ccc(O)CO(C(=O)c2c1)C3c2ccc3	-61.363
81	ZINC06448865	c1ccc(cc1)c2nnc2)SC3c3c(=O)[nH]c4ccc4n3	-92.530	ZINC08773480	Cn1ccc(c1)C(=O)CC(=O)c2ccc3c2c2)[nH]c(=O)[nH]3	-61.296
82	ZINC08733302	c1cc2c(cc1c3cc(n3)C(=O)]O-)]OCCO2	-92.449	ZINC08770056	Cc1c1c2cc(cc2n1)F)CC(C)C(=O)c3ccc3	-61.285
83	ZINC29752537	Cc1nc(=O)n1)COC2ccc2c2)c3nnc3	-92.406	ZINC12446962	Cc1c2c(c(=O)[nH]c1)C(=O)O)CC2=C3c3nH]n3c3c4ccc4	-61.267
84	ZINC32511656	CC(C1nnc1)C2ccc(cc2)OC]N(C(=O)N)3mnc3	-92.364	ZINC19339616	c1ccc(cc1)CN2CC(C)C2)c3cc([nH]n3)c4ccc4)F	-61.222
85	ZINC09290290	Cc1ncc1)N(C(=O)C)C2c2c3ccc(cc3n2)OC	-92.320	ZINC30998725	CN(CCCN(C=O)N)C1CCCC1)c2ccc2	-61.095
86	ZINC27660342	c1ccc(cc1)c2c([nH]c2)SC3c3nc(n3)N]N	-92.290	ZINC19835578	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)C3nc(c3)C4ccc4	-61.089
87	ZINC20943066	Cn1c2ccc(cc2o1)N3c4ccc4c3c5nn3	-92.231	ZINC17885173	c1ccc2c(c1)ccc(n2)C3c3(=O)[nH]c4ccc4n3	-61.049
88	ZINC20638614	c1ccc2c(c1)CC(C2)C(=O)NCC3c3nH]c(=O)cc3)N	-92.213	ZINC07844423	Cc1ccc(c1)C1c2ccc3c2)OC3)C)4ccc4n4)NC	-60.906
89	ZINC09167821	Cc1nnc1)N(C(=O)c2ccc3c2c2)[nH]c(=O)c(=O)[nH]3	-92.177	ZINC32741542	c1ccc2ccc3c2c(1)N(S3)=O)O)CC5c4n(c1)N]n4	-60.805
90	ZINC35182979	c1ccc2c(c1)c1)C(=O)n2)CC(C(=O)]O-)]n3c3</				

Figure S4. Effect of Compounds on Cancer Cell Growth and Hematopoietic Stem Cell Toxicity. For human cancer cell lines, eight-day colony formation assays were conducted. For CD34+ human cord blood hematopoietic stem cells, at eight days the total number of colonies were counted. At fourteen days, the number of colonies in the following hematopoietic lineages were counted: granulocytic (white blood cells), erythrocytic (red blood cells) and megakaryocytic (platelets), measured by the formation of CFU-GM, BFU-E and CFU-GEMM colonies, respectively. All assays were run in replicates of N=2, data expressed as the mean \pm SD percentage of control. Initial findings meeting stipulated criteria were repeated, also in replicates of N=2. For initial screening, cells were treated with 0 (vehicle), 0.017, 0.12, 0.82, 5.7 and 40 μ M of the denoted compound. For replicate experiments, cancer cells were treated with 0 (vehicle), 0.0061, 0.018, 0.05, 0.16, 0.49, 1.48, 4.4, 13.3 and 40 μ M compound. For cancer cells, compound was added one day after plating. For hematopoietic assays, compound was introduced into semisolid media on the day of plating.

Supplementary Table 4. Efficacy ratios at 40 µM compound for all compounds*

cell line	Dwr2 site				FolC2 site				FolC1 site				Dwr1 site				PRT site				EPSP site			TYLT site				FabG site												
	Dwr2-017	Dwr2-051	Dwr2-069	Dwr2-091	Dwr2-054	FolC2-001	FolC2-005	FolC2-025	FolC2-044	FolC2-048	FolC1-042	FolC1-031	FolC1-020	FolC1-087	FolC1-100	Dwr1-021	Dwr1-083	Dwr1-070	Dwr1-026	Dwr1-005	PRT-009	PRT-031	PRT-044	PRT-051	PRT-089	EPSP-023	EPSP-044	EPSP-065	TYLT-001	TYLT-003	TYLT-051	TYLT-072	TYLT-088	FabG-033	FabG-035	FabG-036	FabG-045	FabG-073		
HT116	0.08	0.63	0.93	0.88	1.06	0.60	0.70	0.97	0.93	1.20	0.51	0.82	0.23	0.84	1.17	0.95	1.00	1.16	0.92	0.96	0.86	0.98	0.98	0.84	0.77	1.06	0.93	0.85	0.83	1.07	1.07	1.18	0.92	1.13	1.02	0.99	1.40	1.18		
H729	0.00	0.00	0.01	1.03	0.85	0.79	0.06	0.85	0.00	0.87	0.10	0.86	0.12	0.89	1.09	0.59	0.90	1.08	1.04	0.81	0.91	0.91	1.19	1.07	1.00	0.82	0.99	0.83	0.74	1.16	1.17	2.05	1.15	1.07	0.74	0.80	1.04	0.72		
MCF-7	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.98	0.76	0.43	0.33	1.09	0.01	1.06	0.64	1.22	0.01	0.81	0.91	0.81	0.62	0.95	0.91	0.89	0.65	0.93	0.98	0.85	0.21	0.98	0.91	1.03	0.59	0.48	1.07	0.98	0.63	0.79	1.04	0.67	0.86	1.02		
MDAMB231	0.00	0.05	0.59	-	0.81	0.28	0.78	-	0.16	-	0.65	0.70	0.65	-	0.62	1.10	-	-	-	0.79	0.91	0.75	0.99	0.79	-	-	-	0.85	0.60	1.38	0.97	1.32	-	-	0.48	0.85	0.94			
H226	0.02	0.10	0.03	0.90	1.35	0.00	0.11	0.98	0.00	1.09	0.01	1.06	0.26	1.05	0.94	1.26	0.79	1.08	0.76	0.82	0.83	0.57	0.93	1.11	0.57	-	0.81	0.80	0.75	0.59	1.26	0.14	0.99	0.98	0.89	0.17	0.33	0.97		
4549	0.07	0.96	0.15	0.90	1.10	0.53	0.69	1.19	0.15	1.25	0.96	1.08	0.89	0.84	0.90	0.72	0.99	1.03	0.95	0.92	0.89	0.87	0.92	1.17	0.98	1.03	0.85	1.04	0.79	0.86	1.30	1.17	0.98	1.04	0.76	0.67	0.92	0.89		
PC3-M	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.94	0.69	0.41	0.00	1.12	0.00	1.19	0.18	1.04	0.13	0.90	0.97	0.38	1.13	1.05	1.01	1.00	0.81	0.80	1.00	1.04	0.87	0.99	1.05	1.02	1.01	0.89	0.97	0.99	1.16	1.06	0.78	0.80	1.06	0.93		
LNcap	0.05	0.40	-	-	-	0.34	0.28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
combined data																																								
relative activity for a given compound, %	100	75	71	0	0	63	63	0	100	0	43	0	73	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
relative activity for a given site	3 of 5 (60%) compounds active				3 of 4 (75%) compounds active				2 of 5 (40%) compounds active				1 of 5 (20%) compounds active				0% active				0% active			1 of 5 (20%) compounds active				0% active												

*efficacy ratio = % viable cancer cell line colonies/% viable bone marrow colonies, at 8 days; all assays were run in replicates of N=2 and resultant means used for calculations; those with an efficacy ratio of below 0.5 are denoted in blue font
 †those with efficacy ratio <0.5 were considered active

Figure S5. The Efficacy Ratio of All Compounds and All Cancer Cell Lines Tested. Cancer cells and human bone marrow stem cells were treated with the indicated compound at 40 μ M, and the resultant efficacy ratio is shown. The efficacy ratio = (percent of remaining cancer cell colonies)/(percent of remaining bone marrow colonies), at 8 days after treatment.

Developmental Therapeutics Program

NSC: D-767026 / 1

Conc: 1.00E-5 Molar

Dxr2-017

One Dose Mean Graph

Experiment ID: 1209OS39

Developmental Therapeutics Program

NSC: D-767024 / 1

Conc: 1.00E-5 Molar

FoIC2-001

One Dose Mean Graph

Experiment ID: 1209OS39

150 100 50 0 -50 -100 -150

Figure S6. NCI-60 cell line screens. COMPARE plots for Dxr2-017 and FolC2-001 are shown.

Figure S7. Dxr2-017 increases floating cells and does not alter adherent cell morphology. Cells were treated for eight days with Dxr2-017 at concentrations close to the IC50 value for each cell line examined. Depicted are representative light photomicrographs at 20X; scale bar is 150 µm. Green arrows denote floating cells.